

New ^{13}C -detected experiments for the assignment of intrinsically disordered proteins

David Pantoja-Uceda and Jorge Santoro*

Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano, CSIC, Serrano 119, 28006 Madrid, Spain.

* Corresponding author. Fax: +34 91 564 24 31

e-mail: jsantoro@iqfr.csic.es

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Abstract

NMR assignment of intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) by conventional HN-detected methods is hampered by the small dispersion of the amide protons chemical shifts and exchange broadening of amide proton signals. Therefore several alternative assignment strategies have been proposed in the last years. Attempting to seize that dispersion of ^{13}C ' and ^{15}N chemical shifts holds even in IDPs, we recently proposed two ^{13}C -detected experiments to directly correlate the chemical shifts of two consecutive $^{13}\text{C}'$ - ^{15}N groups in proteins, i.e. without mediation of other nuclei. Main drawback of these experiments is the interruption of the connection at prolines. Here we present new ^{13}C -detected experiments to correlate consecutive $^{13}\text{C}'$ - ^{15}N groups in IDPs, hacacoNcaNCO and hacaCOncanCO, that overcome this limitation. Moreover, the experiments provide recognition of glycine residues, thereby facilitating the assignment process.

Introduction

Many proteins or protein domains (intrinsically disordered proteins, IDPs) lack a well defined secondary and tertiary structure under functional conditions (Dunker et al. 2008; Fink 2005; Tompa 2002, 2011, 2012; Uversky et al. 2000). NMR spectroscopy is probably the most powerful technique for characterizing IDPs (Dyson and Wright 2001, 2004; Eliezer 2009; Fink 2005; Jensen et al. 2009) as it provides information at atomic resolution on both local and long-range conformational behavior on timescales varying over many orders of magnitude. Sequential assignment is a prerequisite for this NMR-based characterization. Conformational averaging of IDPs results in poorly dispersed amide ^1H chemical shifts and in clustering of the $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ and $^{13}\text{C}\beta$ chemical shifts around the random coil value for each amino acid residue type, difficulting the sequential assignment of IDPs with the methods established for globular proteins (Permi and Annala 2004; Sattler et al. 1999). Therefore, several alternative assignment strategies have been proposed in the last years (Bermel et al. 2005, 2009, 2012a; Kumar and Hosur 2011; Hiller et al. 2007; Mäntylähti et al. 2010, 2011; Motackova et al. 2010; Novacek et al. 2012; Sahu et al. 2014; Solyom et al. 2013; Wen et al. 2011). Many of these strategies make use of the long relaxation times that IDPs present as a result of the high flexibility of the disordered polypeptide chain, which allows designing experiments involving multiple coherence transfer steps. However, most of these approaches continue to use the poorly dispersed $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$, $^{13}\text{C}\beta$, or amide proton chemical shifts for the sequential assignment.

Trying to exploit that the ^{15}N and $^{13}\text{C}'$ signals remain well dispersed in IDPs (Dyson and Wright 2001; Yao et al. 1997; Zhang et al. 1997) for the sequence specific assignment, we recently have proposed (Pantoja-Uceda and Santoro 2013a) two ^{13}C -direct detected experiments, hNcocaNCO and hnCOcaNCO, that allow to directly correlate two consecutive C'-N groups in proteins, i.e. without mediation of other nuclei. Main shortcoming of these experiments is the interruption of the connection at prolines, since the experiments use the amide protons as the starting point of the magnetization transfer pathway. Shortly thereafter, Bermel et al. (2013) have proposed alternative experiments for correlating successive C'-N groups, 5D $h^{\text{N-flip}}\text{nCONCACON}$, 5D hcaCONCACON and 5D hCACONcaCON . The experiments use a bidirectional coherence transfer and generate two kinds of peaks: auto-correlated peaks ($^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i-1)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$ in the first two experiments and $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i-1)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$ in the third) and sequential peaks ($^{13}\text{C}'(i-2)-^{15}\text{N}(i-1)-^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i-1)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$ in the first two experiments and $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i-2)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-2)-^{15}\text{N}(i-1)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$ in the third), which provide the information for the

sequential assignment. Although the experiments involve the chemical shift labeling of the poorly dispersed $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$, it is only used to minimize the occurrence of overlap, and 4D versions of the experiments can also be used to establish the sequential connectivity. As in the two last experiments the amide protons are not included in the magnetization transfer, the sequential assignment is not interrupted by the presence of proline residues in the protein sequence, and are therefore better suited to the sequential assignment of IDPs, as many of them are composed of proline-rich polypeptide segments (Marsh and Forman-Kay 2010, Radivojac et al. 2007, Romero et al. 2001). Here we present a new pulse sequence for correlating consecutive C'-N groups that, maintaining this positive feature, offer some advantages over these latter. First, the novel pulse sequence has fewer coherence transfer steps, resulting in an increased sensitivity. Also, our pulse sequence uses a unidirectional coherence transfer pathway. Therefore, as uninformative auto-correlated peaks do not appear in the spectra, the number of observed peaks is reduced, diminishing the spectral crowding.

Materials and Methods

NMR experiments were performed at 18.8 T on a Bruker AV spectrometer operating at 800.1 MHz ^1H , 201.18 MHz ^{13}C and 81.07 MHz ^{15}N frequencies, equipped with a cryogenically cooled triple-resonance (^1H , ^{13}C , ^{15}N) TCI probehead and pulsed z-field gradients. A sample of 0.6 mM uniformly ^{13}C , ^{15}N labeled Nupr1 in 10 mM acetate buffer at pH 4.5 was used to test the experiments. All experiments were acquired at 298 K. Parameters specific to the pulse sequence are reported in the caption of Figure 2. For ^{13}C band-selective $\pi/2$ and π pulses Q5 (or time reversed Q5) and Q3 shapes (Emsley and Bodenhausen 1992) of durations of 307.2 and 192 μs , respectively, were used, except for the π pulse that should be band-selective on the $\text{C}\alpha$ region (Q3, 784 μs) and for the adiabatic π pulse to invert both C' and $\text{C}\alpha$ (smoothed Chirp (Böhlen and Bodenhausen 1993), 500 μs , 20% smoothing, 80 kHz sweep width, 12.5 kHz rf field strength). The ^{13}C band-selective pulses on $\text{C}\alpha$ and C' were given at the center of corresponding region and the adiabatic inversion pulse was adjusted to cover the entire ^{13}C region. Decoupling of ^1H and ^{15}N was achieved with waltz-16 (Shaka et al. 1983) (4.5 kHz) and garp-4 (Shaka et al. 1985) (0.83 kHz) sequences, respectively. All pulsed field gradients employed had 1 ms of duration and a sine shape. The States-TPPI method was applied in all indirect dimensions to achieve quadrature detection. All experiments employ the IPAP approach (Bermel et al. 2005; Bertini et al. 2004) to remove the splitting caused by the $\text{C}\alpha$ -C' couplings in the direct dimension. The

in-phase (IP) and antiphase (AP) components were acquired and stored in an interleaved manner, doubling the number of FIDs recorded (Bermel et al. 2006, 2008).

3D spectra were recorded with spectral widths of 11 ppm and 35 ppm centered at 173.5 ppm and 121.5 ppm for $^{13}\text{C}'$ and ^{15}N , respectively. The 3D spectra were acquired with 512 complex points in the direct dimension and 28 complex points in both indirect dimensions, using 8 transients per FID and a recycle delay of 1 s. The total acquisition time for each 3D spectrum was 20 h. The programs NMRPipe (Delaglio et al. 1995) and NMRView (Johnson and Blevins 1994) were used for spectral processing and data analysis, respectively.

Results and discussion

Description of the pulse sequence

Main drawback of the HNCOCANCO pulse sequence (Pantoja-Uceda and Santoro 2013a) lies in the absence of correlations in which the magnetization starts at prolines. A naive way to overcome this limitation consists in starting from $^1\text{H}\alpha(i)$ coherence, transfer the coherence to $^{15}\text{N}(i+1)$ via $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)$ and $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$, and follow from there the original sequence. Therefore, the coherence should follow the pathway $^1\text{H}\alpha(i)-^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i)-^{15}\text{N}(i+1)-^{13}\text{C}'(i)-^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$. This naive sequence requires several magnetization transfer steps more than the original one, so that a significant loss in sensitivity is expected. However, a careful analysis of this sequence allows its optimization, so that its sensitivity approaches that of the original sequence. Indeed, in the original sequence the passage through the $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$ serves two purposes: labeling the signal with the $^{13}\text{C}'$ chemical shift and allowing the unidirectional transfer from $^{15}\text{N}(i+1)$ to $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)$. In the modified sequence the labeling can be obtained in the first passage over $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$, that also allows the unidirectional transfer from $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)$ to $^{15}\text{N}(i+1)$. Thus, the second passage through $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$ can be omitted, if a way to make directly the back transfer from $^{15}\text{N}(i+1)$ to $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)$ is found. This unidirectional transfer is easily achieved if the $^1\text{J}_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}'}$ coupling is not refocused in the period in which the coherence resides in $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$, so that the $^{15}\text{N}(i+1)$ coherence produced from it is antiphase with respect to both $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$ and $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)$ i.e. of the form $4\text{N}_y(i+1)\text{C}'_z(i)\text{C}\alpha_z(i)$. Therefore the optimized new sequence must perform the coherence transfers $^1\text{H}\alpha(i)-^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i)-^{15}\text{N}(i+1)-^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)-^{15}\text{N}(i)-^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$, as is schematically shown in Figure 1. Although this sequence still has one coherence transfer step more than the original one, as we will see in the description that follows, its sensitivity approaches that of the original sequence.

The pulse sequence that performs the above described coherence transfer steps is given in Figure 2. The pulse sequence starts with an INEPT coherence transfer from the $^1\text{H}\alpha$ spin to its directly attached $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ spin, after which the relevant density operator is

$$2\text{H}\alpha_z(i)\text{C}\alpha_y(i) \quad (1)$$

During the following delay, set to $1/2J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}\beta}$, the $^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{H}\alpha}$ is refocused and the $^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}'}$ defocused, producing the coherence

$$2\text{C}\alpha_y(i)\text{C}'_z(i) \Gamma_1 \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma_1 = n \sin(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{H}\alpha}\tau_2) \cos^{n-1}(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{H}\alpha}\tau_2) \sin(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}'}) \cos^{2-n}(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}\beta}\Delta_1) \exp[-2\Delta_1/T_2(\text{C}\alpha)]$ (n is the proton multiplicity of the α -carbon, i.e. 2 for glycine and 1 otherwise). Then, a pair of 90° pulses applied to $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ and $^{13}\text{C}'$, transfer the coherence to the $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$ spin. The ensuing period serves to label the coherence with the chemical shift of $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$ and to defocus the $^1J_{\text{C}'\text{N}}$ coupling giving the density operator

$$4\text{C}\alpha_z(i)\text{C}'_y(i)\text{N}_z(i+I) \cos(\omega_{\text{C}'(i)}t_1) \Gamma_1\Gamma_2 \quad (3)$$

where $\Gamma_2 = \sin(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}'\text{N}}\Delta_2) \exp[-2\Delta_2/T_2(\text{C}')]$. Next, the coherence is transferred to ^{15}N transverse magnetization, labeled with the chemical shift of the $^{15}\text{N}(i+I)$ spin in a real time mode and converted back into a $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)$ coherence, defined by the density operator

$$4\text{C}\alpha_y(i)\text{C}'_z(i)\text{N}_z(i+I) \cos(\omega_{\text{C}'(i)}t_1) \cos(\omega_{\text{N}(i+I)}t_2) \exp[-t_2/T_2(\text{N})] \Gamma_1\Gamma_2 \quad (4)$$

Next, the $^{13}\text{C}\alpha(i)$ magnetization evolves the $^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{N}}$ and $^2J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{N}}$ couplings and refocus the $^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}'}$ coupling. The density operator terms that can end into observable magnetization are

$$[2\text{C}\alpha_x(i)\text{N}_z(i+I) \Gamma_3 + 2\text{C}\alpha_x(i)\text{N}_z(i) \Gamma_4] \cos(\omega_{\text{C}'(i)}t_1) \cos(\omega_{\text{N}(i+I)}t_2) \exp[-t_2/T_2(\text{N})] \Gamma_1\Gamma_2 \quad (5)$$

where $\Gamma_3 = \sin(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}'}) \cos(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{N}}\Delta_3) \cos(2\pi^2J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{N}}\Delta_3) \cos^{2-n}(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}\beta}\Delta_3) \exp[-2\Delta_3/T_2(\text{C}\alpha)]$ and $\Gamma_4 = -\sin(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}'}) \sin(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{N}}\Delta_3) \sin(2\pi^2J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{N}}\Delta_3) \cos^{2-n}(2\pi^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}\beta}\Delta_3) \exp[-2\Delta_3/T_2(\text{C}\alpha)]$. These coherences are converted into ^{15}N magnetization that is refocused with respect to the $^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{N}}$

or ${}^2J_{C\alpha N}$ coupling and dephased with respect to the ${}^1J_{C'N}$ coupling. During this period the coherences are also labeled with the chemical shift of the ${}^{15}N$ spin, and therefore give rise to the density operator

$$2N_y(i+I)C'_z(i) \cos(\omega_{C'(i)}t_1) \cos(\omega_{N(i+I)}t_2) \cos(\omega_{N(i+I)}t_3) \exp[-t_2/T_2(N)] \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_3\Gamma_5 + \\ 2N_y(i)C'_z(i-I) \cos(\omega_{C'(i)}t_1) \cos(\omega_{N(i+I)}t_2) \cos(\omega_{N(i)}t_3) \exp[-t_2/T_2(N)] \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_4\Gamma_6 \quad (6)$$

where $\Gamma_5 = \cos(2\pi^1J_{C\alpha N}\zeta) \sin(2\pi^2J_{C\alpha N}\zeta) \sin(2\pi^1J_{C'N}\Delta_4) \exp[-2\Delta_4/T_2(N)]$ and $\Gamma_6 = \sin(2\pi^1J_{C\alpha N}\zeta) \cos(2\pi^2J_{C\alpha N}\zeta) \sin(2\pi^1J_{C'N}\Delta_4) \exp[-2\Delta_4/T_2(N)]$. Finally, these coherences are transferred to ${}^{13}C'$ magnetization and the ${}^1J_{C'N}$ coupling is refocused before ${}^{13}C'$ detection. The observable magnetization is then

$$C'_x(i) \cos(\omega_{C'(i)}t_1) \cos(\omega_{N(i+I)}t_2) \cos(\omega_{N(i+I)}t_3) \exp[-t_2/T_2(N)] \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_3\Gamma_5\Gamma_7 + \\ C'_x(i-I) \cos(\omega_{C'(i)}t_1) \cos(\omega_{N(i+I)}t_2) \cos(\omega_{N(i)}t_3) \exp[-t_2/T_2(N)] \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_4\Gamma_6\Gamma_7 \quad (7)$$

where $\Gamma_7 = \sin(2\pi^1J_{C'N}\Delta_5) \exp[-2\Delta_5/T_2(C')]$. To improve resolution in the direct detected dimension, during the final refocusing period the IPAP method of virtual homodecoupling (Bermel et al. 2005; Bertini et al. 2004) is introduced. In summary, there are two pathways that end in observable magnetization, ${}^1H\alpha(i) \rightarrow {}^{13}C\alpha(i) \rightarrow {}^{13}C'(i) \rightarrow {}^{15}N(i+I) \rightarrow {}^{13}C\alpha(i) \rightarrow {}^{15}N(i+I) \rightarrow {}^{13}C'(i)$ and ${}^1H\alpha(i) \rightarrow {}^{13}C\alpha(i) \rightarrow {}^{13}C'(i) \rightarrow {}^{15}N(i+I) \rightarrow {}^{13}C\alpha(i) \rightarrow {}^{15}N(i) \rightarrow {}^{13}C'(i-I)$, giving rise to an auto-correlated and a sequential peak. The intensity of the auto-correlated peak, omitting the small intensity loss associated with the INEPT transfer from ${}^1H\alpha$ to ${}^{13}C\alpha$, is proportional to

$$I_{\text{auto}} \propto \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_3\Gamma_5\Gamma_7 \quad (8)$$

and that of the sequential peak to

$$I_{\text{seq}} \propto \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_4\Gamma_6\Gamma_7 \quad (9)$$

Overall transfer efficiencies of 0.006 for the auto-correlated pathway and 0.133 for the sequential pathway have been calculated using values of 140, 15, 53, 10.6, 7.5 and 35 Hz for the ${}^1J_{C\alpha H\alpha}$, ${}^1J_{NC'}$, ${}^1J_{C\alpha C'}$, ${}^1J_{C\alpha N}$, ${}^2J_{C\alpha N}$ and ${}^1J_{C\alpha C\beta}$ couplings, respectively, 200, 100 and 200 ms for the

transverse relaxation times of ^{15}N , $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ and $^{13}\text{C}'$ spins (Mäntylähti et al. 2011) and the delays given in the caption of Figure 2. The value used for Δ_3 , 28 ms, optimizes I_{seq} and practically suppress the auto-correlation peak, which otherwise would cause unnecessary crowding of the spectra with redundant information. Moreover, the value employed for Δ_1 , 13.5 ms, inverts the sign of the peaks when residue i is glycine. This feature allows to easily identify glycine residues, helping in the assignment process. Therefore, the new pulse sequence has advantages over our previous pulse sequence (Pantoja-Uceda and Santoro, 2013a), namely the presence of all $^{13}\text{C}'$ - ^{15}N correlations and the recognition of glycine residues. The price to pay is a reduction in the transfer efficiency, 0.133 versus 0.186. The sensitivity of the new experiment could be increased if delays $\Delta_1 = 4.7$ ms and $\tau_2 = 4.7$ ms were employed and the $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ 180° pulse in the center of the $2\Delta_1$ period were substituted by a 180° selective pulse affecting only the $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ chemical shift range in order to avoid the evolution of the $^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}\beta}$ coupling. In this case the transfer efficiency would increase to 0.160. However, the $^1J_{\text{C}\alpha\text{C}\beta}$ coupling would evolve when residue i is serine or threonine, drastically reducing the transfer efficiency for these residues. Therefore, we prefer not to use this alternative implementation.

The described experiment, hacaCONcaNCO, corresponds to a 4D spectrum, which demands a very long experimental time to obtain satisfactory resolution, unless non-uniform-sampling methods are used. However, the same information is available from two 3D experiments, hacacoNcaNCO showing the correlation $^{15}\text{N}(i+1)$ - $^{15}\text{N}(i)$ - $^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$ and hacaCONcaNCO displaying the correlation $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$ - $^{15}\text{N}(i)$ - $^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$. This approach requires a much shorter experimental time, and is the one we have used.

Correlation of consecutive C'-N groups can also be obtained with the 5D (HCA)CONCACON experiment (Bermel et al. 2013). Theoretical calculation for this experiment, using the parameters given above, gives a transfer efficiency of 0.101 for the sequential peak and 0.035 for the auto-correlated peak. Evolution of the $^1J_{\text{NC}\delta}$ coupling of prolines during the first period in which the magnetization resides in ^{15}N will reduce these figures by about 33% in the case of the Pro-Xxx sequential peaks and of the proline auto-correlated peaks. Therefore, the new proposed experiment shows a clear sensitivity advantage in the case of IDPs. Furthermore, the absence of auto-correlated peaks in our experiment produces less congested spectra, which is also advantageous.

Application and assignment protocol

We have applied the novel experiments in concert with a 2D CON spectrum to complete the assignment of Nupr1, an IDP of 93 residues we used to illustrate the hNcocaNCO and hnCOcaNCO experiments. Figure 3 exemplifies the assignment protocol. The procedure starts from a $^{15}\text{N}(i)$ - $^{13}\text{C}'(i-1)$ correlation peak observed in the 2D CON spectrum. The coordinates of this peak are used to locate the chemical shift of $^{15}\text{N}(i+1)$ in the 3D hacacoNcaNCO spectrum and the chemical shift of $^{13}\text{C}'(i)$ in the 3D hacaCONcaNCO spectrum. These two chemical shifts identify a peak in the 2D CON spectrum, corresponding to the next amide linkage in the protein sequence. Using this process iteratively, employing each time the coordinates of the last incorporated CON peak, a chain of consecutive residues of increasing length is constructed. This daisy chaining stops when one of the following conditions is reached:

- a) No following CON peak is obtained. This situation appears when the chain reaches the C-terminal residue, but also may occur because the signals in the 3D spectra are too weak to be properly observed.
- b) The method provides more than one possible successor. This case arises when two or more amide linkages have very similar $^{13}\text{C}'$ and ^{15}N chemical shifts, so that the corresponding peaks overlap in the 2D CON spectrum. In this situation none of the potential successors is added to the chain.
- c) The new CON peak coincides with the first CON peak of a chain previously obtained. In this case both chains are merged.

Once a stopping condition is reached, the process is repeated starting from an unused CON peak. The process of building chains is continued until all peaks in the CON spectrum have been used. Advantages of the new pulse sequences are clearly illustrated in Fig 3, where the sequential peaks $i-i+1$ absent in the hNcocaNCO and hnCOcaNCO spectra when residue $i+1$ is a proline (Pantoja-Uceda and Santoro, 2013a) are visible. The sequential specific assignment is thus not interrupted by the presence of prolines. Furthermore, the sign of the correlation peaks allows to identify glycines. These two advantageous features of the new pulse sequences have allowed us to confirm our previous assignment of Nupr1 (Aguado-Llera et al. 2013, Pantoja-Uceda and Santoro, 2013a) and complete it.

In an ideal case the described protocol will end with a single stretch of length equal to the number of residues of the protein minus one. Therefore the matching of this stretch to the protein sequence will be obvious. In other cases, however, the protocol will result in several stretches. So, the matching of the stretches to the protein sequence requires some additional information. In this respect, the identification of glycines provided by the experiment is very useful. Furthermore the prolines, that can be identified by its characteristic ^{15}N chemical shift or by comparing 2D

CON spectra starting from ^1HN and starting from $^1\text{H}\alpha$, can be used to check the correctness of the matching or as additional anchor points. If this information is not enough to properly determine the matching, more anchor points can be obtained by running some of the CAS-NMR experiments (Bermel et al. 2012b), that give CON spectra containing correlations arising from a particular type of amino acid residue. Alternatively a β -carbon edited CON experiment (Pantoja-Uceda and Santoro, 2013b), which classifies all CON correlations into 6 groups using a single experiment, can be used.

Conclusions

In this manuscript we have presented two novel ^{13}C -detected 3D experiments for the sequence-specific assignment of IDPs. The sequential specific assignment is performed correlating the $^{13}\text{C}'$ and ^{15}N chemical shifts of two consecutive amide linkages. The new experiments overcome the limitations of our previous pulse sequences (Pantoja-Uceda and Santoro, 2013a), namely the absence of correlations in which the magnetization starts at prolines, at a moderated cost in sensitivity. A further advantage of the new experiments is the identification of glycine residues. The recently published 5D (HCA)CONCACON pulse sequence (Bermel et al. 2013) also yields all the correlations between consecutive C'-N groups. However, our sequence offers several advantages: larger magnetization transfer efficiency and absence of auto-correlation peaks, therefore decreasing spectral crowding. Moreover, our approach is not based on a high dimensional experiment using non-uniform sampling, so it is accessible to users who do not have access to this technique.

During the development of our pulse sequence the group of Permi (Hellman et al. 2014) has published a similar pulse sequence, (HCA)CON(CAN)H, which differs from ours in the final coherence transfer step and uses ^1H -detection. Although the ^1H -detection implies an increase in the intrinsic sensitivity of the experiment, their use is not without disadvantages. First, it is not possible to detect the correlations in which the magnetization ends at proline. Furthermore, in the case of IDPs the amide protons typically exchange rapidly with the water, thus giving rise to wide or even absent signals (Hsu et al. 2009). Also, the amide proton signals of IDPs show poorer dispersion than those of $^{13}\text{C}'$, so the sequence-specific assignment will be more difficult. Finally, the amide proton signal is a doublet due to coupling with $^1\text{H}\alpha$, while that of the $^{13}\text{C}'$ is a singlet if the IPAP virtual decoupling technique is applied. Moreover, the $^{13}\text{C}'$ signals are narrower than those of the amide protons. These last facts together with the existence of ^{13}C -detection optimized probes partially compensate the intensity loss.

Pulse sequences for the experiments in Bruker language can be obtained from the web page <http://rmnpro.iqfr.csic.es>.

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Figure captions

Fig 1 Schematic representation of the magnetization transfer pathway implemented in the hacaCONcaNCO experiment. The colored nuclei are used to correlate residues i and $i+1$. Arrows indicate the magnetization transfer pathway

Fig 2 Scheme of the hacaCONcaNCO pulse sequence. The arrows indicate the switching of the ^{13}C carrier frequency. All radiofrequency pulses are applied along the x-axis unless indicated. 90° and 180° rectangular pulses are represented by filled and unfilled bars, respectively. ^{13}C pulses have the shape of gaussian cascades Q5 (90° , black filled shapes) and Q3 (180° , open shapes) with durations of 307 ms and 192 ms at 800 MHz, respectively. The simultaneous $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ and $^{13}\text{C}'$ pulses indicated in grey correspond to an adiabatic inversion pulse over the $^{13}\text{C}'$ and $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ regions, Chirp, 500 μs , 25 % smoothing, 80 kHz sweep, 10.0 kHz strength. Decoupling of ^1H and ^{15}N and were achieved with waltz-16 (4.5 kHz) and garp-4 (0.83 kHz), respectively. The delays employed are: $\tau = 1.8$ ms; $\tau_2 = 2.4$ ms ; $\eta = 4.5$ ms; $\Delta_1 = 13.5$ ms; $\Delta_2 = 15.0$ ms; $\Delta_3 = 28.0$ ms; $\zeta = 14.0$ ms; $\Delta_4 = 15.0$ ms; $\varepsilon = t_2(0)+p$, where p is the duration of the adiabatic ^{13}C pulse. The delays of the IPAP element are: $\varepsilon_1(\text{IP}) = \Delta_5/2$, $\varepsilon_1(\text{AP}) = \eta$, $\varepsilon_2(\text{IP}) = \Delta_5/2$, $\varepsilon_2(\text{AP}) = \Delta_5-\eta$, $\varepsilon_3(\text{IP}) = \Delta_5/2$, $\varepsilon_3(\text{AP}) = \Delta_5-4 \mu\text{s}$, $\varepsilon_4(\text{IP}) = \Delta_5/2$, $\varepsilon_4(\text{AP}) = 4 \mu\text{s}$, with $\Delta_5 = 15.0$ ms. Pulsed field gradients g_1 to g_3 of sinusoidal shape are applied along the z-axis with a 1 ms length and amplitudes of 50%, 30% and 19% of the maximal intensity of about 50 G/cm. Phase cycle: $\phi_1=16(x), 16(-x)$; $\phi_2=8(x), 8(-x)$; $\phi_3= 2(x), 2(-x)$; $\phi_4= 4(x), 4(-x)$; $\phi_5= x, -x$; $\phi_6= x(\text{IP})$ or $-y(\text{AP})$; $\phi(\text{receiver})= x, 2(-x), x, -x, 2(x), 2(-x), 2(x), -x, x, 2(-x), x, -x, 2(x), -x, x, 2(-x), 2(x), 2(-x), x, -x, 2(x), -x$. Good results are obtained using only the first 4 steps of the phase cycle.

The 3D hacaCONcaNCO experiment is performed by setting t_1 to 0 and omitting the $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ 180° pulses labeled with an asterisk. Quadrature detection in the indirect dimensions is achieved by incrementing phases ϕ_2 and ϕ_5 in a States-TPPI manner. To perform the 3D hacacoNcaNCO experiment t_2 is fixed to 0 and the adiabatic inversion pulse labeled with an asterisk is omitted. In this case, quadrature detection in the indirect dimensions is achieved by incrementing phases ϕ_3 and ϕ_5 in a States-TPPI manner.

Fig 3 Illustration of the method for assigning the protein $^{13}\text{C}'$ and ^{15}N resonances. Starting from a ^{15}N - $^{13}\text{C}'$ correlation observed in a 2D CON spectrum, the ^{15}N and $^{13}\text{C}'$ chemical shift values of the succeeding residue are obtained from the sequential cross peaks in the hacacoNcaNCO and

hacaCOncanCO spectra, respectively. Assignment is exemplified using the residues 21-27 of Nupr1. In top of each panel the ^{15}N frequency that has been fixed to extract the particular F1-F3 plane are reported. Sequential connections Xxx-Pro (highlighted with red arrows), absent in the hNcocaNCO and hnCOcaNCO spectra, are here visible. Note also that the negative sign of the sequential correlations observed in the last cross-section identify the residue as a glycine.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

